

POLICY BRIEF

Executive Summary

Funded by the European Union

The lack of use of non-custodial sentences is slowing down justice systems and overloading judges and prosecutors, forcing them to make quick verdicts. The list of existing alternative measures in countries of the European Union is lengthy, and yet very few alternatives are used. Accordingly, the purpose of the Policy Brief is to highlight the necessity of limiting the excessive usage of pre-trial detention and the adoption of alternative measures. These are the proposed recommendations for reducing pre-trial detention in practice:

1. Further training of judges and prosecutors on alternative measures.
2. More cooperation between EU Member states is crucial in order to limit the discrepancy in practice currently present.
3. Cohesive time limits need to be set on all alternative measures, while being periodically revised.